

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT TREND OF THE INDUSTRIAL POTENTIAL OF THE REGION

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Abstract: *This article discusses the concepts of potential, economic potential and industrial potential. The methods of analysis of factors influencing the development of industrial potential are considered. In addition, proposals have been developed for the analysis of indicators reflecting the industrial potential of the Samarkand region.*

Key words: *industry, efficiency, production, potential, indicators, method.*

INTRODUCTION

In most developing countries, urgent tasks include the further development of industrial potential and the analysis of factors affecting it, and the identification of features, the improvement of the organizational and legal framework for innovative development, the assessment of economic potential, and the identification of the current state and trends in management mechanisms.

Industrialization is also growing rapidly in Uzbekistan. In particular, in 2020, enterprises of the republic produced industrial products worth 367.1 trillion soums, which is 100.7% more than in 2019, 105.0% more than in 2018, and 110.8% more than in 2017 [1].

This growth trend in industrial production is based on the technical and technological renewal of the industry's enterprises, as well as ongoing comprehensive reforms.

Because the modernization and diversification of production is an important condition for ensuring and strengthening economic security. Accordingly, the national industrial potential is growing as a result of successive promising projects [2].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

In general, the concept of potential in a broad sense is a concept that can be used to solve any problem, for example, tools, resources, available resources and their mobilization, mobilization, achievement of a specific goal, implementation of a plan.

Potential is an objectively existing system consisting of several interrelated elements, each of which requires proper assessment and scientific management; efficiency of capacity use depends on the quality of management of factors separated by their composition, depending on the potential element, the state of the external and internal environment[3].

When it comes to economic potential, there are different points of view and recognition.

For example, according to R. Sadykova, the economic potential is explained by the welfare of the population. That is, it is the sum of all the possibilities and tools for achieving economic development[4].

The economic potential is an important basis for the organization of the national, regional economic system. The volume of economic potential reflects the development of productive forces, the competitiveness of the country, the level of capitalization of enterprises. This is done through the development of the following factors [5].

Factors affecting economic potential

A structural element of potential		
Natural resource potential	Intellectual potential	Infrastructure potential
Investment potential	Social potential	Financial potential
External economic potential	Innovative potential	Industrial potential

It should be noted that economic potential can be traditionally described as the overall efficiency of natural resources, labor resources and material and technical resources.

The economic potential of the region as a whole system can be expressed as the potential of the following basic reproductive elements [6]:

Hence, the economic potential of the region can be expressed in the following structure (Fig.1).

Fig.1

Structure of the economic potential of the region [7]

In general, such terms as "potential", "production" and "economic potential of the region" can be found a lot in economic literature and research, and they have many definitions.

However, in the economic literature, "industrial potential" has recently become widespread, and its content is interpreted in different ways. It should be noted that in order to understand the industrial potential, it is necessary to clearly identify its organizational structure.

According to E. Zadorozhnaya, industrial potential includes innovation potential, infrastructure potential, financial potential, material and technical potential, labor potential and investment potential [8].

Indeed, there are key indicators that reflect the potential of the industry. These include the volume of industrial output (Q_s), labor productivity in industry (M_u), the efficiency of the use of fixed assets in industry (A_s), the efficiency of investment in industry (I_{ns}) and the innovative potential in industry (I_s).

Therefore, if the industrial potential consists of the above indicators, then the mathematical expression of the industrial potential (S_s) can be given as follows.

$$S_s = \sum(Q_s + M_u + A_s + I_s + I_{ns}) \quad (1)$$

In general, the analysis of regional industrial potential is a methodology that helps to identify industrial sub-sectors that have the potential for future competitiveness and economic growth of the region.

It should be noted that the assessment and study of industrial potential makes it possible to identify the main directions of management and development of industry, their advantages and disadvantages, while the following methods can be used (Table 1).

Methods of assessing industrial potential

Valuation Approaches	Assessment type	Method description	Application of the method	Disadvantages
Expert	Quality	Analysis of structural elements in the form of interviews, questionnaires	It is used when it is necessary to take into account the influence of certain quality factors	The reliability of the assessment is determined by the powers of the experts, the assessment may be subjective.
Resources	Quantity	The amount of resources spent on industry was determined. The essence of industrial potential is defined as the results of production.	They give a quantitative picture of the object under study, making it possible to determine the influence of each element on the composition of the industrial potential.	does not take into account changes in quality
Efficiency				
Statistical analysis	Quantity	Indicators representing industrial potential are analyzed on the basis of	Allows quantitative measurement, study and analysis of	It does not provide clear recommendations for further industry potential building

		statistical methods	industrial potential	
Econometric analysis	Quantity	The influence of factors on the industrial potential is analyzed on the basis of economic-mathematical and econometric methods.	It is used to predict and express the quantitative dependence of the influence of factors on industrial potential.	There are inconsistencies in the modeling of some processes with a high upward trend in the indicators used

The results of the analysis show that at present there is no universal methodology that takes into account quantity and quality. The use of only one direction within the framework of the methodology does not provide a reliable assessment due to the presence of production potential and qualitative and quantitative characteristics. For example, there is no vision of opportunities to intensify labor and increase productivity without taking into account the number of labor resources and their qualifications.

However, the study and analysis of not only industrial potential, but also factors affecting industrial potential, based on econometric methods, i.e., a quantitative assessment of the influence of factors on industrial potential, is important in developing a strategy for further building up industrial potential. This is due to the fact that it will be possible to quantify the impact of each factor on industrial potential. This allows us to present clear directions for the further development of the industry.

Benefits of econometric analysis of industrial potential

So, if the industrial potential is mainly the volume of industrial production (Q_s), labor productivity (M_u), the efficiency of the use of fixed assets and (A_s), investment efficiency (I_s), we will give an estimate of the industrial potential for the Samarkand region.

The results of the analysis allow to group the districts (cities) of the region on the basis of labor productivity in industry, investment in industry and efficiency of fixed assets using the method of statistical grouping. Grouping of districts of Samarkand region according to indicators of industrial potential

№	Indicator	Top group ($M_u \geq 100$)	Middle group ($100 > M_u \geq 50$)	Bottom group ($50 > M_u$)
1	Labor productivity in industry	Samarkand, Jambay, Taylak	Kattakurgan, Aqdarya, Bulungur, Narpay, Pastdargom, Pakhtachi, Samarkand, Nurabad, Urgut	Ishtikhon, Kattakurgan, Qoshrobat, Payariq
		$(I_s \geq 10)$	$(10 > I_s \geq 5)$	$(5 > I_s)$
2	Efficiency of investment in industry	Bulungur, Kattakurgan, Payariq	Jomboy, Narpay, Samarkand	Samarkand, Kattakurgan, Aqdarya, Ishtikhon, Koshrobat, Pastdargom, Pakhtachi, Nurabad, Urgut, Taylak
		$(A_s \geq 10)$	$(10 > A_s \geq 5)$	$(5 > A_s)$
3	Efficiency of fixed assets in industry	Kattakurgan, Payariq	Narpay, Pastdargom, Pakhtachi, Samarkand, Urgut	Samarkand, Kattakurgan, Aqdarya, Bulungur, Jambay, Ishtikhon, Koshrobat, Nurabad, Taylak

CONCLUSION

Based on the foregoing, it should be noted that when determining the prospects for its further development based on the development trends of the region's industries and their structural and statistical analysis, it is advisable to take into account the following:

1. It is necessary to modernize and diversify existing industrial enterprises and provide comprehensive support for the production of high-tech products;
2. Based on the socio-economic conditions of the region, it is necessary to accelerate the financing of the creation of new industries based on modern technologies at the expense of banks and other sources;
3. Improving the market for online industrial products based on digital technologies and bringing it to the international level, etc.

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